

Synthesis and crystallographically characterized thiadiazole derivative as an efficient Fe³⁺ selective fluorescent probe

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Abstract : A thiadiazole derivative, 2-((naphthalen-2-yl)methylthio)-5-((naphthalen-7-yl)methylthio)-1,3,4 thiadiazole (L₁) has been synthesized and well characterized by different analytical techniques, viz. ¹H NMR, QTOF mass spectra, elemental analysis, FTIR and, its structure has been confirmed by single crystal X-ray structure analysis. Two naphthalene units of two molecules in a unit cell are parallel to each other through π-π stacking interaction while S atoms are involved in n-π* interaction with vacant π* orbital of naphthalene unit. The binding of L₁ with Fe³⁺ has been established from FTIR, thermal and mass spectral analysis of the product. The composition of the complex (Fe³⁺: L₁ = 1 : 1, mole ratio) in solution has been evaluated by Job's plot. The probe has been used for trace level determination of Fe³⁺ by fluorescence technique. L₁ has an excitation and emission maxima at 370 nm and 440 nm respectively. The binding constant of L₁ for Fe³⁺ has been estimated from Stern-Volmer method as 7.9 × 10³. The limit of detection is 8 × 10⁻⁷ M.

Keywords : Fluorescent probe, Fe³⁺, thiadiazole derivative, X-ray structure.

Introduction

Iron is well known essential intracellular metal ion which plays a vital role in a variety of cell functions¹. Iron is mainly distributed in hemachrome, which occupied 60–70% of total iron in a body. Additionally, it plays a central role in the biosphere and serves as the active center of proteins responsible for O₂ and electron transfer. It is also essential for forming some kinds of biotic enzymes (such as catalase)². Determination of trace amounts of Fe³⁺ is of great importance as its deficiency or excess can induce a variety of diseases like anemia, liver and kidney damage, diabetes, and heart failure^{3,4}. Iron homeostatis is an important factor involved in the neuro inflammation and progression of Alzheimer's disease^{5,6}. The environmental and biological effectiveness of iron depends on its chemical properties, such as valence, solubility, and the degree of chelation or complex formation. Growth of bacterial infections and marine ecosystems is regulated by the amount of bioavailable iron^{7–10}. Several methods have been reported for detecting iron including atomic absorption spectroscopy¹¹, colo-

rimetry¹², spectrophotometry^{13–15} and voltammetry¹⁶ techniques, which generally require sophisticated equipment, tedious sample preparation procedures, and trained operators. Recently, the fluorescent method has become very popular due to its operational simplicity, high selectivity, sensitivity, rapidity, nondestructive methodology and direct visual perception¹⁷. Despite immense importance of Fe³⁺ in many biochemical processes at the cellular level, till date only a few Fe³⁺ sensitive fluorescent sensors have been reported^{18–26}. Fe³⁺, being a paramagnetic ion, can quench the fluorescence of a probe. Recently, the fluorescent sensors for Fe³⁺ have been the subject of a series of investigations^{4,20,27}. But most of the reported Fe³⁺ selective fluorescent probes require tedious multi-step synthetic protocols and thus expensive. Herein, we present a naphthalene based 2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L₁) derivative as a highly selective and sensitive fluorescent probe for Fe³⁺ which has been synthesized in a single step from low cost commercially available precursors. The fluorescence quenching of L₁ is occurred due to its interaction with paramagnetic Fe³⁺.

The fluorescence quenching behavior is a typical Stern-Volmer static quenching²⁴ with a binding constant (K) of $7.9 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Materials :

2,5-Dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazol, dipotassium salt and 2-bromomethyl naphthalene are purchased from Merck (Dramstadt, Germany) and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents are of analytical grade and used without further purification. Water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$) from Milli-Q purification system (Bedford, MA, USA) has been used throughout all the experiments. Fe^{III} stock solution (500 mg L^{-1}) have been prepared from $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ (Merck, Dramstadt, Germany) in demonized water. This solution was standardized against standard stock solution of Fe^{III} (1000 mg L^{-1}) supplied by SOLUTIONS plus inc. (Missouri, USA) which was tested vs NIST SRM # 3108a using AAS. The working solutions of Fe^{III} have been prepared by successive dilution of the stock solution. The sources of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Ag^+ , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} ions are either their chloride or nitrate or perchlorate salts.

Apparatus and physical measurements :

^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 with a Bruker Advance 300 MHz using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. Absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded on Shimadzu Multi Spec 1501 absorption spectrophotometer and Hitachi F-4500 fluorescence spectrophotometer, respectively. Mass spectrum was recorded in QTOF Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer in ESI positive mode. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FTIR spectrophotometer (model : FTIR-H20). Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on a Perkin-Elmer TG/DTA lab system 1 (Technology by SII). A single crystal of the dimension $0.70 \text{ mm} \times 0.18 \text{ mm} \times 0.13 \text{ mm}$ has chosen for X-ray diffraction study. Crystallographic measurements have been made at $100(2) \text{ K}$ by using a STOE IPDS-II two-circle diffractometer. Intensities are corrected for Lorentz polarization and for absorption. The structures are solved by direct methods. Hydrogen atoms bound to carbon are idealized. Structural refinements have been performed with full-matrix least-squares based on F^2 by using the program SHELXL²⁸. Hydrogen atoms are mostly discernible in difference Fourier maps and could be refined to reasonable geometry. According to common practice they are nevertheless kept in ideal positions during the refinement.

Synthesis of 2-((naphthalen-2-yl)methylthio)-5-((naphthalen-7-yl)methylthio)-1,3,4 thiadiazole (L_1) (Scheme 1) :

Dimethylformamide (DMF) solution of 2-bromomethyl naphthalene (585.85 mg, 2.65 mmol) was added slowly to the solution of 2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazol, dipotassium salt (300 mg, 1.325 mmol) in DMF. The mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature. The clear mixture was poured into cold water to get white curdy precipitation which was filtered and recrystallized to get a pure crystalline product. It was characterized by ESI-TOF mass spectra, ^1H NMR spectra, FTIR spectra and finally by single crystal X-ray structure analysis. ESI-TOF-MS (+) Calcd. for L_1 ($\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{S}_3$) : 430.1 (M); Found : 453.07 [$\text{M} + \text{Na}$]⁺ (Fig. S1). Selective FT-IR data (cm^{-1}) : ν C-O_{alkyl} (1385.47), ν C-O_{aryl} (1052.39) (Fig. S2). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) (Fig. S3) : δ (ppm), 4.65 (4H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 7.46–7.50 (6H, m, ArH), 7.78–7.83 (8H, m, ArH). Yield, 92%.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of L_1 and its Fe^{3+} complex.

Synthesis of $L_1\text{-Fe}^{3+}$ complex (Scheme 1) :

Methanol solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ (70.84 mg, 0.2 mmol) is added dropwise to a solution of L_1 (86 mg, 0.2 mmol) in methanol. The mixture is stirred for 1 h followed by reflux for about 4 h. The wine red color mixture is kept for 3 days to obtain crystalline compound, which is characterized by ESI-TOF-MS, FTIR spectra and TGA. ESI-TOF-MS (+) Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_9\text{S}_3\text{Cl}_2$: 701.9 (M); Found : 724.75 [$\text{M} + \text{Na}$]⁺ (Fig. S4); % Fe : 8.1 (Calcd. 7.9). Selective FTIR data (cm^{-1}) : ν_s ClO_4 (1051, 1088, 1112, 1145); ν_a ClO_4 (627) (Fig. S5). Yield, 71%.

Measurement procedures :

The fluorescence spectra of L_1 ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and L_1 with different metal solutions are measured at

Fig. S1. ESI-TOF MS (+) spectrum of L₁.

Fig. S2. FTIR spectrum of L₁.

Fig. S3. ¹H NMR spectrum of L₁ (inset expanded for aromatic region).

Fig. S4. ESI-TOF mass spectrum of [L₁-Fe³⁺] complex.

Fig. S5. FTIR spectrum of [L₁-Fe³⁺] complex.

room temperature. The solutions of Fe³⁺ and L₁ are mixed in different ratios for subsequent fluorescence measurements keeping the solution composition same for all the sets viz. MeOH : water (9 : 1, v/v). 1.00 cm quartz cell is used for this purpose.

Results and discussion

Single crystal X-ray structure of L₁ and spectroscopic studies :

Figs. 1 and 2 present the ORTEP view and crystal packing diagram of L₁ respectively. The title compound

crystallizes in the monoclinic space group P 2₁/n. The density (ρ) of the single crystal is 1.428 g cm⁻³ and the *R* factor (final) of the single crystal is 0.0366. Fig. 2 shows that naphthalene units of two molecules in a unit cell are parallel to each other through π - π stacking interaction while non-bonding electrons on S atom of one molecule interacts with vacant π^* orbital of the neighbor naphthalene unit of another molecule. C(19)-S(18) and S(12)-C(11) bond lengths are 1.828(2) Å and 1.828(2) Å respectively, which are close to carbon-sulfur single bond. The bond angles S(18)-C(19)-C(20) and S(12)-C(11)-C(1)

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of L₁ (50% thermal ellipsoid probability).

Fig. 2. Crystal packing of L_1 .

are 105.66(14) and 105.93(13) respectively, which are consistent with the sp^3 hybrid character of C(19) and C(11) atoms. C15-S(18)-C(19) and C11-S(12)-C(13) bond angles are 105.66(14) and 105.93(13) respectively, which also indicate the sp^3 hybrid character of S(18) and S(12) atoms. Relevant crystallographic parameters are summarized in Table 1. The selected bond lengths and bond angles of L_1 have shown in Table 2.

Fig. 3 shows the excitation ($\lambda_{ex} = 370$ nm) and emission ($\lambda_{em} = 440$ nm) spectra of L_1 . Stokes shift ($\lambda_A - \lambda_F$) is an important parameter indicating the difference in properties and structure between the ground state (S_0) and the first excited state (S_1) of the fluorophore. The value of stoke shift for L_1 was 3745 cm^{-1} . Except Fe^{3+} , which significantly quenched the emission intensity of L_1 , no other cations viz. Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Ag^+ , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} had changed the emission intensity of L_1 . Only Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} increased the fluorescence intensity of L_1 to a negligible extent (Fig. 4). Loss of π - π stacking and n - π^* transition by the intervention of Fe^{3+} , are the causes for static fluorescence quenching of L_1 . Fig. 5 shows the changes in the emission intensity of L_1 (1×10^{-5} mol L^{-1}) as a function of added $[\text{Fe}^{3+}]$ (1×10^{-4} mol L^{-1} to 1×10^{-3} mol L^{-1}). Plot of fluorescence intensities vs externally added $[\text{Fe}^{3+}]$ (Fig. 6) reveals that up to 100 times (1×10^{-3} mol L^{-1}) of the externally added $[\text{Fe}^{3+}]$, the fluorescence intensity of L_1 decreases exponentially.

Table 1. Single crystal X-ray structural and refinement parameters for L_1

Crystal parameters	Ligand (L_1)
Molecular formula	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{S}_3$
Formula weight	430.58
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 21/n
a (Å)	18.146(4)
b (Å)	6.0488(14)
c (Å)	19.879(5)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	113.353(3)
γ (°)	90.00
Z	4
V (cm^3)	2003.2(8)
T (K)	100(2)
λ (Å)	0.71073
ρ (g cm^{-3})	1.428
μ (mm^{-1})	0.384
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.70 \times 0.18 \times 0.13$
$h/k/l$	$-22, 20/0, 7/0, 24$
$F(000)$	896
θ range (°)	1.95 to 26.45
GOF	1.055
T_{min} and T_{max}	0.7749 and 0.9518
Reflection collected	4124
Independent reflection	4124
Data/restraints/parameters	4124/0/262
R factor (all data)	0.0547
R factor (final)	0.0366
Largest peak and hole ($\text{e}^{\text{Å}}^{-3}$)	0.290 and -0.224

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for L₁

Bond distances (Å)		Bond angles (°)	
C19-S18	1.828(2)	C1-C11-S12	105.93(13)
S18-C15	1.745(2)	C11-S12-C13	100.20(9)
C15-S14	1.737(2)	S12-C13-S14	119.78(11)
C15-N16	1.294(3)	S12-C13-N17	125.48(16)
N16-N17	1.391(2)	S14-C15-S18	119.89(11)
N17-C13	1.297(3)	C15-S18-C19	99.77(10)
C13-S14	1.740(2)	S18-C15-N16	124.99(15)
C13-S12	1.737(2)	S18-C19-C20	105.66(14)
S12-C11	1.827(2)		

Fig. 3. Excitation and emission spectra of L₁ (10 μM, λ_{ex} = 370 nm, λ_{em} = 440 nm).

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of L₁ (10 μM) in MeOH in presence of 1000 μM different ions in binary mixtures.

Fig. 5. Changes of the fluorescence spectra of L₁ (10 μM, λ_{ex} = 370 nm, λ_{em} = 440 nm) in MeOH as a function of added [Fe³⁺].

Fig. 6. Fluorescence intensity vs [Fe³⁺].

Further addition of Fe³⁺ has no effect on the emission intensity of the system. Limit of detection is 8×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹. Job's plot indicates the 1 : 1 stoichiometry for the L₁-Fe³⁺ complex (Fig. 7). Bidentate chelating binding mode of ClO₄⁻ in the inner-sphere of [L₁-Fe³⁺] complex is evident from the splitting of unassociated perchlorate (outside coordination sphere, ionic at 1088 cm⁻¹) into three components viz. 1145, 112 and 1051 cm⁻¹ ²⁹.

Estimation of binding constant :

The relationship between the fluorescence quenching (I_0/I) to [Fe³⁺] obeys the Stern-Volmer equation³⁰, I_0/I

Fig. 7. Job's plot of complexation between L₁ and Fe³⁺ indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry (mole ratio) in MeOH.

= 1 + K [Q] where, I₀ is the fluorescence intensity of free L₁, I is the fluorescence intensity of the [L₁-Fe³⁺] complex, Q is [Fe³⁺] and K is the binding constant. The binding constant of L₁ with Fe³⁺ is 7.9 × 10³ (Fig. 8) indicating a fair interaction between them. Fig. 9 shows the changes in the binding constant of L₁ and Fe³⁺ as a function of ligand concentration [L₁] (1 × 10⁻⁶ mol L⁻¹ to 10 × 10⁻⁶ mol L⁻¹).

Fig. 8. Stern-Volmer plot for determination of binding constant of L₁ (10 μM) with Fe³⁺.

Selectivity :

The selectivity behavior is obviously one of the most important characteristics of an ion-selective chemosensor,

Fig. 9. Binding constant of Fe³⁺ with different concentration of L₁.

which is the relative optode response for the primary ion over other ions present in the solution. Thus, the influence of a number of common metal ions on the fluorescence intensity of the proposed Fe³⁺ sensor is investigated. In Fig. 10, effect of foreign metal ions on the fluorescence intensity of the L₁-Fe³⁺ system is presented. Increase in the fluorescence intensity compared to the L₁-Fe³⁺ system upon addition of foreign cations is disig-

Fig. 10. Interference of foreign cations.

nated as positive interference and the reverse phenomenon as negative interference. In this study, [L₁] = 10⁻⁵ mol L⁻¹, [Fe³⁺] = 5 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹ and the added foreign metal ions are 1 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹. Fig. 10 reveals

that except Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , which have very little positive interference, none other cations interfered. The definite reason for selective fluorescence quenching of L_1 by Fe^{3+} is not clear, however, extent of spin orbit coupling may be responsible. Again, suitable chelating environment restricts chelation between L_1 and diamagnetic cations.

Thermal studies :

Stability of $\text{L}_1\text{-Fe}^{3+}$ complex towards temperature is studied by thermogravimetry (TGA/DTG) to prove the binding event of Fe^{3+} ion with L_1 . Results are presented in supplementary materials (Fig. S6 and Fig. S7). It is clear from the graphs that from 28.52 °C to 169.02 °C,

Fig. S6. Thermogram of L_1 .

Fig. S7. Thermogram of $[\text{L}_1\text{-Fe}^{3+}]$ complex.

Fig. S7a. Percentage (%) weight loss of $[L_1-Fe^{3+}]$ complex.

the weight loss is 12.132% which may be due to the loss of one outer sphere perchlorate ion. Similarly from 169.02 °C to 183.64 °C, 2.56% weight loss may be due to the escape of inner sphere H_2O molecule. Finally, 24.87% weight loss from 247.80 °C to 330.64 °C, may be due to loss of two inner sphere coordinated perchlorate ions. Thus from FTIR, mass spectra and TGA analysis, the most plausible composition of the $[L_1-Fe^{3+}]$ complex is portrayed as $[Fe(L_1)(ClO_4)_2(H_2O)]ClO_4$.

Estimation of Fe^{III} from different synthetic mixtures :

Different sets (each set in duplicate) having different amounts of Fe^{III} in a total volume of 100 mL are analyzed for direct estimation of Fe^{III} using the developed method. The results are presented in Table 3.

No. of observations	Amount of Fe^{III} taken (μg)	Amount of Fe^{III} found (μg)	Error (%)
1.	30	29.3 ± 0.08	2.31
2.	66	64.5 ± 0.11	2.27
3.	100	97.8 ± 0.06	2.20
4.	150	147.0 ± 0.00	2.00

Conclusion

Naphthalene anchored thiadiazole (L_1) derivative has

been established as efficient fluorescent probe for Fe^{3+} ion. The probe has been well characterized by different spectroscopic tools and single crystal X-ray structure analysis. The method is virtually interference free. The probe has a fairly good binding affinity towards Fe^{3+} in aqueous methanol solution. The method has the potentiality to be used for trace level determination of Fe^{3+} in different environmental and biological samples.

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Supporting information

CCDC 821535 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html> (or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12, Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223-336033). Thermal, FTIR, 1H NMR, and TOF-MS spectra of L_1 and its Fe^{3+} complex are available here.

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